

THE UNIVERSITY *of* EDINBURGH
Centre for Data, Culture & Society

CDCS ANNUAL REPORT

2022-2023

2022-2023

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HELLO!

WE ARE DELIGHTED TO BE SHARING THE FOURTH ANNUAL REPORT OF THE CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY, WHICH DOCUMENTS OUR ACTIVITIES SUPPORTING DATA-LED AND DIGITAL RESEARCH OVER THE LAST ACADEMIC YEAR.

While last year's report looked back over our achievements since launch, this year our focus is on the future. 2022/23 has been a period of significant change for CDCS: we have found a new context for our work as part of the 'innovation platform' within the Edinburgh Futures Institute, and we also saw our founding Director Melissa Terras come to the end of her term of office. We have been using this period of transition to take stock of our work so far, gather thoughts and explore what our next phase of activities should look like. We are excited about the future and pleased to be able to begin sharing some of our plans in this report.

Alongside this reflective work, the CDCS team has been as busy as ever and this report lays out an impressive amount of activity. Our new Rapid Prototyping Sandpit was a highlight this year and saw us support fifteen data-led projects in their next technical steps. We continue to offer an expansive and varied training programme from which hundreds of researchers benefit and delivered our third CDCS Summer School in June. With two streams and students attending from across Scotland, this was significantly larger than last year. We've also enjoyed bringing our community together at events: our third annual lecture - given by author and activist Nanjala Nyabola - was another highlight, as was the award ceremony for our 2023 Digital Research Prizes. We continue to see data-led research growing and thriving around us and are proud of the role we are playing in stimulating and supporting our community.

Collaboration is at the heart of CDCS and this year has also seen us working with others across the University, the UK and beyond. We have strengthened relationships with research groups, organisations and networks and worked to deliver projects with a variety of partners. This all points forward to exciting future activities, as we grow our profile and begin to contribute on larger stages.

A WORD OF THANKS

It was the vision, drive and energy of our founding Director, Professor Melissa Terras, that got CDCS off the ground and set our pace and direction. Melissa envisaged a more joined up approach to supporting digital research within CAHSS, and she brought that vision to life. Her passion for digital research is infectious and her belief that the arts, humanities and social sciences have a vital role to play in an increasingly digitised and digital world remains our guiding principle. On behalf of the whole CDCS community, I would like to thank her for the vital work she has done in establishing the Centre and developing a thriving digital research community within CAHSS. Although Melissa has now demitted, we are delighted that our working relationship will continue as she joins the Centre's new academic Advisory Board.

CDCS activity is a collective effort at every level, and many hands and minds are responsible for the work presented in this report. Particular thanks goes to Lucia Michielin, who delivers a stronger and bigger training programme each year and leads on the coordination of our growing summer school. Our administrators Likando Kumoyo and Laura Murray provide seamless support for our website, events and admin processes and ensure that the CDCS machine is oiled and running well. Dr Jessica Witte, working with us as an EFI Postdoctoral Research Fellow, has been instrumental in developing our support offer this year and we greatly value her proactive approach to researcher engagement. Ed McKenzie, who joined the team as a Research Technologist in January has contributed a wealth of new ideas and skills to the team. We benefit enormously from the input of the twelve School Leads who have sat on our Core Team, and will form the basis of our new Advisory Board going forward. I'd like to thank five of these Leads in particular as they pass the baton on in 2023: Mike Fuller, Beverley Hood, Morgan Currie, Galina Andreeva and Jon Henderson have all been excellent colleagues and have made valuable contributions over the last four years.

Since 2019, we have also benefited from the insight, guidance and encouragement of a Steering Group which will now be disbanded as we move our reporting into EFI structures: I'd like to thank all those who have sat on the Steering Group, and in particular Professor Sarah Prescott, whose support during this transition period has been constant and much appreciated.

A final thanks goes to Professor Chris Speed, Director of EFI, and Jude Henderson, EFI's Chief Operating Officer: they have offered great insight, support and enthusiasm as we've considered the possible futures of CDCS and, along with many other EFI colleagues, have given us a warm welcome as we've come into the fold. We're looking forward to working more closely together as CDCS moves into the new EFI building later this year.

DR LISA OTTY

Director

CDCS PEOPLE

LISA OTTY
DIRECTOR

LUCIA MICHELIN
Digital Research Skills
Training Manager

ED MACKENZIE
Research Technologist

JESSICA WITTE
Postdoctoral Research
Fellow

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MELISSA TERRAS
Founding Director, Professor
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BEATRICE ALEX
Edinburgh Futures Institute
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Literatures and Cultures

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School of Economics

ORIAN BROOK
School of Social and Political
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School of Informatics

REBECCA HIRSCH
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School of Philosophy,
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SAM LEGGETT
School of History, Classics
and Archaeology

BEN MOEWS
Business School

PHIL SHEAIL
Moray House School of
Education and Sport

LACHLAN URQUHART
Edinburgh Law School

NEW PHD AFFILIATES

GREGG LLOREN
Edinburgh College of Art

YOUSSEF AL HARIRI
School of Informatics

DAVID MESA-RUIZ
School of Economics

ALBERT SHARRA
School of Social and Political Science

MATTHEW TANNAM-ELGIE
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ASH CHARLTON
School of History, Classics and
Archaeology

**CLAUDIA GONZÁLEZ-
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ANAND RANJAN
School of Divinity

MARTIN CHENG
Business School

PATRICIA WU WU
Edinburgh College of Art

PHD AFFILIATES

AGANA-NSIIRE AGANA
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VICTORIA EVANS
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ELLEN FRANK DELGADO
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LUCY HAVENS
School of Informatics

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School of Social and Political Science

ASAD KHAN
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WENLONG LI
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YI LI
School of Literatures, Languages
and Cultures

ANDREW MCLEAN
School of History, Classics and
Archaeology

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School of Social and Political Science

JOSEPH NOCKELS
School of Literatures, Languages
and Cultures

ADAM FERRON
School of Literatures, Languages
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RESEARCH AFFILIATES

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The Alan Turing Institute

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Humanities, University College
London

GEORGE OATES
Executive Director & Founder of The
Flickr Foundation

KEVIN GLYNN
Associate Professor in Geography &
Environmental Sciences, Northumbria
University

SUZANNE BLACK
Postdoctoral Researcher, Creative
Informatics, University of Edinburgh

SCOTT B. WEINGART

EVENTS

ONLINE, IN PERSON & HYBRID

Bringing people together to share their work and discuss projects is always a pleasure: we love to see the sparks of new ideas emerging and to help new collaborative relationships bloom. We were thrilled to be able to host our annual lecture in person for the very first time this year, and to showcase the work of our community by staging two new data-led artistic performances as part of the EFI events programme. People from all around the world continued to attend our online events and we welcomed local researchers back to our informal fikas and socials.

WHICH WAY TO THE QUICKEST EXIT? LESSONS FROM THE GLOBAL SOUTH ON RESTORING THE POSSIBILITIES OF THE INTERNET

Nanjala Nyabola

This year's annual lecture showed how far-reaching and complex questions of morality and humanity entwine with our day to day use of platforms, as activist and writer Nanjala Nyabola reflected on the impact and harms caused to many, particularly in the Global South, by these technologies and the companies that own them.

EFI EVENTS

WHAT MY BODY CAN/T REMEMBER

In her performance, dancer, choreographer and University of Edinburgh PhD student Farah Saleh explored the ways in which memories are recorded, stored, retrieved and re-shaped over time. Her work invited us to consider the difference between how memories are captured or 'saved' using technology and how memories are encoded into the human body by experience.

IT'S ALL ABOUT THE FEELINGS...

Our second contribution to the EFI public events programme was a thought-provoking piece by artist Bev Hood and actor Pauline Goldsmith, which reflected on AI attempts to read and analyse human emotion, showing its biases and limitations through a live engagement with emotion recognition software.

COLLABORATIVE EVENTS

**DIGITAL HUMANITIES CLIMATE COALITION: TOOL KIT LAUNCH AND NEXT STEPS **

The Digital Humanities Climate Coalition launched a new toolkit to support researchers in understanding and minimising the environmental impact of their work.

**IMAGINING ARTIFICIAL LIFE: BREAKING THROUGH THE SCREEN **

We partnered with our friends at IASH to contribute an event to the Being Human Festival.

**THE FLICKR FOUNDATION'S 100 YEAR PLAN **

We co-hosted a workshop for the Flickr Foundation exploring what a 100-year plan for a cultural organisation might look like.

FIKAS & SOCIALS

One of the things we've all missed in the last few years has been opportunities for informal networking, chatting with new people and relaxing together over a drink and some food. So we've brought back our PhD socials and our fikas (which are cake and coffee mornings) this year: it's been brilliant to finally meet in person with some of the new researchers who have joined our community in the last few years.

SEMINAR SERIES

We've welcomed our community back to in-person events alongside our online seminars, attracting people from all around the globe.

Towards Large-scale Cultural Analytics in the Arts and Humanities Project Findings

Melissa Terras, Rob Baxter, Brendan Miles, Rosa Filgueira, Suzanne Black

Book Launch: Millicent Garrett Fawcett: Selected Writings

Melissa Terras and Elizabeth Crawford

Allusions, Algorithms, and the Mind: Observations from a Computational Approach to Reading Poetry

James Gawley

Decolonizing Knowledge Production through Linked Open Data

Jennifer Guiliano

Moral Horizons of Pain: Participatory Theatre and Public Engagement with Data and Technology in Medicine

Ariel Ducey, Pratim Sengupta, Martina Ann Kelly, Santanu Dutta and Erin Knox

Stories of the Syrian New Scots: Digital Storytelling in COVID-19 Refugee Arts

Annie Webster

Self-assessment and self-reflection in the European cultural heritage sector and its role in fostering digital transformation

Fiona Mowat

Re-materializing the Digital: Governmentality and the Environmental Consequences of Life Online

Dipali Mathur

Protecting Confidentiality When Accessing History

Louise Neilson

Anti-slavery archives, networks, and distributed data: The Case of Mary Anne Rawson's The Bow in the Cloud (1834)

Christopher Ohge

Uncertainty in Crowdsourced Digital History Projects: The Operation War Diary

Andrea Kocsis

REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY

- 1-10 REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY
- 10-50 REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY
- 50-100 REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY
- 100+ REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY

REGISTRATIONS BY CONTINENT

"IMMENSELY ENJOYED NANJALA'S TALK. [IT WAS] INTERESTING AND APPROACHABLE [AND] ENCOURAGED REFLECTION AND HUNGER TO RESEARCH MORE ON THE THEME. OVERALL SUPERB."
SEMINAR ATTENDEE

TRAINING

BUILDING DATA SKILLS.

It's been another year of growth for our training programme. As well as increasing the size of our team of training fellows, we expanded the list of experts with whom we collaborate on courses in copyright, text analysis, GIS, 3D data, and digitisation. Delivering over 60 training sessions, we maintained a balance between in-person and online training to ensure that we offer courses that are accessible for everyone within our community. We also built on the success of our first summer school, delivering an in-person week-long intensive course in summer 2022 and then doubling in size in 2023 by adding a second stream of teaching.

CDCS TRAINING COURSES: 64

CDCS TRAINING REGISTRATIONS: 1070

TRAINING PROGRAMME

This year we had the highest attendance to date with over 1000 staff and students upskilling with us this year and participating in over 60 courses on topics ranging from structured and unstructured data analysis, introduction to programming, GIS, to digital drawing and 3D data. We were able to achieve this by drawing on the expertise of our Training Fellows and colleagues from EDINA, Library, LLC, ECA, University Collections, and uCreate Studio.

NEW TRAINING PATHWAYS

We are committed to helping researchers orient themselves and learn new methods, that's why we develop our Training Pathways which lay out the steps involved in learning new skills and point towards relevant courses and resources. Recent additions cover the topics of Statistical Analysis and Text Analysis, as well as Managing Digitised Documents and Working with 3D Data. Another pathway on Geographical Data is currently under development.

REUSABLE MATERIALS

We support the reuse of training material and create open educational resources that can benefit others. In 2021 we created our GitHub organisational page for hosting all the material we produced during the year. We now have 42 repositories and 20 people have contributed to the growth of our project.

OUR CORE TOPICS

- Digitised documents & text analysis
- Intro to programming
- Data wrangling & data visualisation
- Structured data analysis
- Geographical data
- Digital drawing & 3D data
- Good practices of digital research

CDCS TRAINING FELLOWS 22/23

JAMES BESSE

James is a PhD student in Science, Technology and Innovation Studies. His research concerns the implementation of e-ID systems, specifically looking at the EU Settlement Scheme. He uses text mining alongside social surveys and interviews to understand user experience with the EUSS.

STEFANO BORDONI

Stefano has recently completed a PhD in Architectural Archaeology at the School of History, Classics and Archaeology. In his thesis, he turned the building materials used in medieval Umbria into quantitative data, in order to identify patterns. Through this, he is knowledgeable in photogrammetric surveying, AutoCAD vector drawing, QGIS geoprocessing, RStudio data management and visualisation.

LUCY HAVENS

Lucy is a PhD student based in the School of Informatics, and she researches bias in cultural heritage metadata. Using a collection of case studies within cultural heritage collections (such as the Archives at the University of Edinburgh), she combines natural language processing and data visualisation technologies to identify and classify the bias present in the language of cultural heritage catalogues.

BHARGAVI GANESH

Bhargavi is a PhD student doing interdisciplinary research at the intersection of philosophy, computer science, and public policy. She is affiliated with the Center for Technomoral Futures and the UKRI Research Node on Trustworthy Autonomous Systems Governance and Regulation. She has worked at non-profit research organizations and government institutions, where she studied the impact of housing policies on marginalized groups. In her doctoral research, Bhargavi is developing frameworks to guide the governance and regulation of autonomous systems and decision-making algorithms in various fields including health, robotics, and finance.

PEDRO JACOBETTY

Pedro is a sociologist whose research interests intersect include technology, digital culture, knowledge production and circulation, media and communication. He is also interested in innovative ways of using digital methods for social sciences and art.

ANDREW MCLEAN

Andrew is finishing his PhD at the School of History, Classics and Archaeology. As an archaeologist with research interests currently focused on the economy of the Roman Adriatic, his methodological approaches include GIS and statistical analysis, particularly expanding on traditional Least Cost Path (LCP) analysis by using circuit theory to model maritime movement.

JAMES PAGE

James is an archaeologist whose research focuses on the economy of Northern Italy in the Roman period. His work uses a combination of network modelling and statistical analyses to look at the dynamics behind inland trade and test the validity of prior modelling. He is familiar with QGIS, R, and OpenRefine.

DANIEL WHEELDON

Daniel holds a PhD degree in musicology. He has worked with museums and private collections in the UK, Germany, and USA, using traditional and digital technologies to extract information from original art objects. As a Chester Dale fellow at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (NY), he also took part in a project investigating the efficacy of photogrammetry in studying museum objects.

FANG JACKSON-YANG

Fang is a PhD student at the School of Philosophy, Psychology, and Language Sciences. Her project investigates how speakers encode prominent information in simulated conversations and how listeners predict upcoming utterances in comprehension. She works with both laboratory and corpus data. She conducts data analyses in R using multivariate statistical tools such as mixed-effects models.

BONAN ZHAO

Bonan is a PhD student in cognitive psychology. She studies the twists and turns of how people generalize causal concepts to novel situations. In her research, she builds computational models to simulate human cognition and runs large online experiments to evaluate model predictions with people's judgments. She used to teach programming and web development to refugees in Amsterdam, and has been an enthusiastic advocate of open research practices.

“THE PATIENCE AND STEP-BY-STEP GUIDES FROM BOTH OF THE INSTRUCTORS ARE WHAT MAKES THIS COURSE SO DIFFERENT FROM OTHER CODING COURSES I HAVE TAKEN PREVIOUSLY. FOR THIS PYTHON CLASS, WHICH I WILL HIGHLY RECOMMEND TO MY NETWORK, EVERYONE’S NEEDS ARE CATERED TO.”

PARTICIPANT \ TRAINING PROGRAMME 2022-23

**TEXT & DATA ANALYSIS
SUMMER SCHOOLS 2022 & 2023**

After the success of our online summer school in 2021, we ran our first in-person summer schools. With support from the Scottish Graduate School for Social Sciences and EFI we were able to offer it for free to academic researchers and professionals from across Scotland and beyond. Participants benefitted from presentations and hands-on coding activities in R on the topics of OCR, text analysis, web scraping, sentiment analysis, descriptive statistics, null hypothesis testing, regression, mixed effects modelling, and data visualisation. We ended each day with a BYOD (bring your own data) activity where attendees had the opportunity to work on their own data and get support and feedback from others.

This year we expanded and developed the summer school to cater to a wider array of skill levels, we hosted two streams, one for researchers with no prior knowledge of coding and data analysis, and another designed to help researchers with coding experience understand how data and text analysis projects are performed in a research environment. With a packed schedule covering all things data analysis and a variety of social events, attendees told us that the week was both invaluable and enjoyable.

“PROBABLY THE MOST INTERESTING AND USEFUL TRAINING COURSE I HAVE BEEN ON IN MY CAREER. AN INCREDIBLE OPPORTUNITY.”

**PARTICIPANT **
**TEXT & DATA ANALYSIS SUMMER SCHOOL
2022**

FUTURE FOCUS

HOW WE'RE MOVING FORWARD.

Change is constant but it's been a particular focus for us this year. We've spent time exploring what our community needs now, as it begins to recover from the disruptions of the last few years, and envisioning what we hope to achieve going forward. Fittingly, as we move into the Edinburgh Futures Institute, it's been a time for considering the future of CDCS and the future of digital research methods support. With the help of many colleagues, we've developed a new framework for articulating our work and the contributions we are making, and we've set ourselves some ambitious new goals.

FUTURE FOCUS

LED BY OUR COMMUNITY

We pride ourselves on responding flexibly to meet the needs of our community. Over the last year, we've consulted extensively with stakeholders, research clusters, teams and colleagues across the University, listening to their ideas and getting feedback on our plans. Going forward, our Advisory Board -composed of academics from across CAHSS Schools as well as colleagues from Informatics, Information Services and EFI- will steer the Centre and ensure that we set a direction that supports our whole community's aims and ambitions.

OUR NEW HOME

This year we have been working to align ourselves more closely with other teams and projects within the Edinburgh Futures Institute, and articulate our contribution to the Institute's work. Now, as we all prepare to move into the beautifully redeveloped former hospital on Lauriston Place, it seems like the right moment to embrace the EFI ethos of *challenge, create, change*, and our strategic objectives have been written to reflect this.

OUR STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES 2023 - 2026

Effective Institutional Support

1. INNOVATE IN DIGITAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

We will develop an array of flexible, effective pedagogic models and a supporting framework that ensures consistency and quality.

Effective Institutional Support

2. ESTABLISH A DEVELOPMENT AND PROTOTYPING SERVICE

We will offer new services that help researchers incubate data-led research projects.

Effective Institutional Support

3. DEVELOP EFI RESEARCH TECHNOLOGY SUPPORT

Collaborating with ECA and ISG, we will develop new technical research support services within EFI.

Effective Institutional Support

4. SUPPORT THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELATED METHODS-LED RESEARCH INITIATIVES

We will collaborate to support the development of relevant methods-led research initiatives within CAHSS and EFI, including the Social Data Science Hub and Humanities Informatics.

Communities of Practice

5. SUPPORT THE GROWTH OF COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE

We will build and facilitate new communities of practice around digital methods and datasets within and beyond the University.

Communities of Practice

6. DEVELOP OUR AFFILIATION SCHEMES

Review affiliate and associate schemes and align with EFI schemes.

Communities of Practice

7. STRENGTHEN RELATIONSHIPS WITH SCHOOLS ACROSS CAHSS

We will build deeper partnerships to facilitate interest in and growth in capacity for data-led methods.

Communities of Practice

8. BUILD OUR NETWORKS

Consolidate and grow relationships with partners from across the UK HE skills landscape.

Leading Change

9. DEVELOPING MODELS FOR THE REAL WORLD

We will develop sustainable and challenge-led digital upskilling delivery models.

Leading Change

10. SHARE OUR EXPERIENCE

Share our frameworks for providing engaging digital and data upskilling via publications, collaborative projects, conference presentations and events.

Leading Change

11. BUILDING UP RSE CAPACITY

Develop innovative Research Software Engineering provision model, and engage with national RSE issues and communities.

Leading Change

12. CONTRIBUTE NATIONALLY

We will contribute to the development of a national Digital Research Infrastructure, through engagement with UKRI and strategic projects.

SKILLS

VALUES DRIVE OUR WORK

Our approach to building capacity for data-led and applied digital research is grounded in the values that we hold as a Centre driven by and for researchers in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, from refining the ways we use, create and share open educational resources to exploring how we can co-create more effective learning opportunities. As we begin to explore the contexts opened up by our move into the Edinburgh Futures Institute, we're considering what innovation in training might look like, how cross-sectoral collaboration might play into capacity building, and how we can support skills development in a challenge-led environment. We're excited about the ways we are going to put our ideas into practice going forward.

LEARNING THROUGH REAL WORLD CHALLENGES

It's common practice for trainers to develop their courses by isolating processes and using small, pre-cleaned and simplified data sets: while this ensures learners can focus on the elements being taught, it can lead to a disconnect with real world projects and make it hard for learners to apply their learning outside the classroom. We're interested in how we can support connection between research and technical skills, and in how we can equip our researchers with the skills they'll need to tackle real world challenges.

This year we began to experiment with challenge-led training through our summer school programme. We started by identifying a set of core questions that we wanted to address and developed the course around methods and techniques useful to address these questions. This year's focus was on the cost of living crisis in the UK. In this way, while still focusing on learning new methods and techniques, the attendees were able to better understand how these methods could serve specific research approaches.

A MEETING OF EQUALS

We are driven by our belief in the value of the arts, humanities and social sciences, disciplines which teach us to how to analyse, interpret, create and communicate effectively. Our work is about helping researchers combine these disciplinary skills with the technical skills required to understand, navigate, critique and explore our increasingly datafied and digital world. Our training is developed and led by arts, humanities and social science researchers who have already been through the hurdles of exploring and embedding digital and data-driven methods in their own research and can encourage and support a critical and creative engagement with these tools. We're also contributing to the growth of specialised humanities research software engineering through our work on the DH RSE summer school.

REUSE & RECYCLE

In line with our values, we support the reuse and recycling of training material in multiple ways:

- We continue our collaboration with Programming Historian and we use their peer-reviewed tutorials in our silent disco format.
- Our pathways link together the different steps needed to master a certain method and signpost materials and resources available within the university and beyond.
- We release all the material produced for our training programme online on GitHub. We now have 42 repositories and 20 people have contributed to the growth of our project.

BURSARIES

DIGITAL HUMANITIES @ OXFORD SUMMER SCHOOL

This year PhD Student Ash Charlton attended the Digital Humanities @ Oxford Summer School.

DIGITAL METHODS WINTER SCHOOL

We supported PhD students Ari Stillman and Lara Del Molin in attending Digital Methods Winter Schools.

MSC IN SPEECH AND LANGUAGE PROCESSING

We supported Professor Will Lamb attend training in Speech and Language Processing.

PRIORITISING ACCESSIBILITY

PATHWAYS

One of the challenges researchers face when employing digital methods is identifying and bridging knowledge gaps and practical barriers. To help researchers navigate this complex and sometimes overwhelming landscape, we have built a series of Training Pathways which guide researchers through the steps and concepts they need to master new methodologies while highlighting interconnections between methods. We added two new pathways to the collections this year.

FLEXIBLE FORMATS

Our community is highly multi-disciplinary and encompasses researchers at very different stages of their careers. Not all people learn the same way or have the same amount of time available. So, rather than trying to provide a one-fits-all model, we offer a diverse and flexible range of training opportunities. Our workshops and courses take place at varied times, and in varied formats, some in person and some online. This year, we offered half of our programme online.

SELF-PACED LEARNING

Alongside our standard training, we provide community-focused self-paced learning through our 'Silent Discos' where attendees work through a tutorial at their own pace with an instructor available online to help them with any issues. This year, we held 8 silent discos.

PROJECTS

SUPPORT FOR OUR COMMUNITY

We are creating an environment in which ideas can become reality and in which connections and interchange strengthen our community and our research. From early stage advice to troubleshooting and one-off data surgeries, CDCS is there to support to researchers throughout their data-led and digital research projects. We look for opportunities to help researchers develop useful connections and collaborative partnerships, and help facilitate access to technical expertise across the University.

PROJECTS

INCUBATING NEW IDEAS

Trying a small pilot or building a prototype can be a really useful way to test and scope out digital project requirements, and demonstrate that an idea is feasible. This year we experimented with a new support format to help projects at early stages, with the launch of our Rapid Prototyping Sandpit. We put out an open call asking researchers with digital projects to pitch for some time with our technical team, and then walked them through the process of defining requirements, paper prototyping and then developing minimum viable products. We had a great response to our call and, although not all projects went on to develop prototypes, we were able to assist everyone who applied in outlining and clarifying their next steps.

15

SANDPIT APPLICATIONS

15 researchers applied to take part in the sandpit.

8

PROJECTS SUPPORTED

Eight projects were suitable for the sandpit.

4

PROTOTYPES CREATED

We built four prototypes over the summer.

RESEARCH DATA SURGERIES

Our team offers one-to-one advice to help troubleshoot and get researchers through tricky moments in their project. With a network across disciplines and schools, we can also draw on the experience and knowledge of our community. This year we assisted ten researchers on topics as diverse as rhino models, geo-referencing, statistical modelling and textual analysis.

ENSURING LONG TERM SUSTAINABILITY

Our research technologist has been ensuring the sustainability of long term projects by:

- Collaborating to re-develop the database for the Linguistic Atlas of Late Mediaeval English online project.
- Updating the technical infrastructure on which the Scottish Survey of Witchcraft project operates.

IASH FELLOWSHIPS 2022-23

We partner with IASH to offer funded Digital Scholarship Visiting Fellowships and Digital Scholarship Postdoctoral Fellowships each year.

Visiting Research Fellow

PROF NATHANIEL DOMINY

Paleo Visions of Chauvet Cave: A Virtual Reality (VR) Experience at the Intersection of Art, Anthropology, and Digital Humanities.

Postdoctoral Fellow

DR DIPALI MATHUR

'Rematerializing' the Digital: Governmentality and the Environment Consequences of Life Online.

Postdoctoral Fellow

DR ANNIE WEBSTER

Stories of the Syrian New Scots: Dispersed Geographies and Digital Storytelling in COVID-19 Refugee Arts.

COLLABORATION

BRINGING PEOPLE TOGETHER.

We have an expanding network of partners. This year has seen us deepen our relationships with other skills-focused organisations such as the Programming Historian and the Scottish Graduate Schools, co-develop a Community Interest Group for the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association, and contribute to a range of externally organised events. We've also worked closely with other teams within the University of Edinburgh, hosting an internship with Library and University Collections and ensuring we collaborate to provide seamless support for data-led and digital research.

COLLABORATION

NEW COMMUNITY INTEREST GROUP

The Digital Humanities Climate Coalition, which CDCS helped to establish, has been announced as one of the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association's Community Interest Groups. Co-led by CDCS Director Lisa Otty, the DHCC Community Interest Group will hold workshops, events and a discussion forum to explore the environmental aspects of DH research practice. Through these community-led conversations the CIG will identify appropriate activities and support short term working groups to expand our toolkit and develop complementary materials, raise awareness of the need for climate conscious digital research practices, and build up a knowledge base of relevant resources for the Association's wider membership.

CDCS/CHDS OCR INTERNSHIP

We were delighted to jointly host an internship with the University's Cultural Heritage Digitisation Service this summer. Intern Ash Charlton focused on exploring the current state of Optical Character Recognition and spent time looking at how OCR has advanced and been impacted by machine learning, writing a report for the CHDS team and developing a workshop on OCR for CDCS.

THE PROGRAMMING HISTORIAN

We are proud partners of the Programming Historian project, which makes peer-reviewed self-guided digital humanities tutorials available online. This year we were pleased to have our Training Manager, Lucia Michielin, contribute to UCLDH's online roundtable discussion: 'Where' Affects 'How' We Teach which focused on how digital humanities can be taught through the use of Programming Historian in different global contexts.

SKILLS AND TRAINING COLLABORATIONS

DH RSE SUMMER SCHOOL

Along with Cambridge Digital Humanities, Kings Digital Lab, and Turing Institute, CDCS co-organised the Digital Humanities & Research Software Engineering Summer School, featuring a combination of online talks and in-person workshops hosted by Cambridge Digital Humanities. The content focused on the roles and practices of the Research Software Engineer in Digital Humanities and we contributed sessions on rapid prototyping, high-performance computing, and teaching computational methods.

DESIGN FOR SUSTAINABLE SOCIO-ECONOMIC MODELS: DECODE WINTER SCHOOL

CDCS training fellows designed and delivered 3 masterclasses for the Decode winter school, focused on finding patterns across data, data science in the wild, and network analysis with Gephi. The modules complimented a broader programme of advanced training modules that revised and extended data-driven

notions of optimisation and efficiency and provided participatory methods to support the use of designed artefacts for data-driven value capture and co-creation.

SSI COLLABORATION WORKSHOP

Our training manager collaborated with researchers from across the UK to deliver a workshop on good teaching practices during the Collaboration Workshop 2023. The "Carpentries Superstars: How to Make the Best of Your Teaching Experience helped Carpentries instructors who have not had many opportunities to gain teaching experience to build confidence, give/obtain feedback and understand how they might want to develop and expand their teaching skills.

TECHNE': DIGITALISATION AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH IN SOCIAL SCIENCE

We delivered a presentation on teaching and learning digital methods and skills for cultural heritage at

a workshop run by the Techne' collaborative doctoral training consortium.

SGSAH PHD WORKSHOP: USING DATA IN LEGAL RESEARCH

We contributed to a workshop organised by the Scottish Graduate School for Arts and Humanities, exploring the broad issues arising from engaging in data-based research in the context of legal scholarship. We gave an overview of the types of tools, software and databases that are available for doing data analysis and the practicalities of embedding them in research.

EDINBURGH AND UK CARPENTRIES

CDCS continues its ongoing collaboration with the Carpentries and its Edinburgh branch. Our centre Director sits on the steering committee of Edinburgh Carpentries and our Training Manager sits on the organising committee and collaborates on the monthly UK community call.

INFRASTRUCTURE

MEETING RESEARCH NEEDS

Growing capacity for data-led and digital research means ensuring that the tools, services and support required by researchers are in place. Working with researchers from across different schools and disciplines, we're in the ideal position to identify gaps and help develop a joined up support and service offer. We're aiming to not only improve our local institutional support, but also to develop support models, tools and frameworks that others can use.

GROWING LOCALLY

TEI SERVICE

We operate a hosting service for TEI and other XML projects using eXist-db.

TEI BY EXAMPLE

We host TEI by Example, a set of openly available online tutorials in TEI mark up.

OMEKA SERVICE

We're developing a new Omeka hosting service for online research exhibitions.

NEW TECHNICAL CAPACITY

In January the CDCS team expanded with the addition of Research Technologist Ed McKenzie, who has provided back-end development support for a variety of projects over the last six months. In the coming year, Ed will also start to work as part of a virtual Research Technology support service for the Edinburgh Futures Institute.

CONTRIBUTING NATIONALLY

SSI SOFTWARE SKILLS SURVEY

We fed into the training and skills sections of the SSI AHRC Software Needs report, which was finalised in September 2022.

UK DRI COMMUNITY CONGRESS

We attended the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Community Congress in Birmingham in March 2023.

UK DH INFRASTRUCTURE MAP

We appear on the UK DRI infrastructure map, produced by the Mapping the Arts and Humanities Project led by the School of Advanced Study, University of London.

DIGITAL RESEARCH PRIZES

REWARDING RESEARCH EXCELLENCE

We showcase the amazing data-led and digital work of our researchers through our annual prizes. This year we saw a brilliant set of nominations across the disciplines. Submissions ranged from work on climate change, through conflict and resolution to theatrical performance, and illustrated the incredible innovation, imagination and impact of our community.

BEST SMALL DATA-DRIVEN PROJECT

WINNER

A SPRING AHEAD

Jenny Long, Jiamei Huang and Michaela Yosephine

“This small project has been used to shed a thought-provoking light on an aspect of the climate crisis few are aware of. The project’s results are startling and have wide ranging implications for our understanding of how ecosystems are responding to global heating, with ready potential to scale up the study and apply across different biomes.”

Highly Commended

The Economic Impact of the Menopause

Bee French

BEST IMPACT FROM A DATA-LED PROJECT

JOINT WINNER

BUILDING A COMPREHENSIVE DATABASE OF SCOTTISH FOOD POLICIES

Claire Perier

“As the cost of living crisis continues to impact across the country, our relationship with food, its cost, and its impact on the planet, is ever more relevant. The Food Policy Database’s holistic approach has seen it play a key role in the creation of new government legislation that will transform the way Scotland engages with food.”

JOINT WINNER

DIGITAL LAB FOR ISLAMIC VISUAL CULTURE AND COLLECTIONS AND ASSASSIN’S CREED MIRAGE

Glaire Anderson, Sarah Slingsluff and Deniz Vural

“Of all the submissions this project had the clearest case for large impact, in my opinion.”

“This project is subtly reframing millions of peoples’ understanding of Islamic culture - really significant in terms of impact.”

BEST DATA VISUALISATION

WINNER

UKRAINE DATA TRACKER

Christine Bell, Sarah Schöttler and Jinrui Wang

“The Ukraine Data Tracker offers a haunting visualisation of the ongoing conflict, readily making apparent the devastating scale of the war. This valuable resource will be used by both researchers and lay people, the depth of information contained within made accessible with an easy to use interface.”

“An easy and user-friendly tool that could be tailored to focus on different aspects of the analysed phenomenon. Also, a very timely project that could help users in visualising an ongoing issue”

Highly Commended

Global Diffusion of Songs on Spotify

Tod Van Gunten and Aybuke Atalay

BEST DATASET

WINNER

PA-X PEACE AGREEMENTS DATABASE AND DATASET (SIXTH RELEASE)

Christine Bell, Sanja Badanjak, Laura Wise, Robert Wilson, Juline Beaujouan, Adam Farquhar and Jennifer Hodge

“This expansive dataset is more relevant than ever, serving to remind us that peaceful resolutions are still possible in a world increasingly ravaged by conflict. The extraordinary breadth of data gathered here offers the tools for future peacemakers to learn from and apply past successes to current resolutions.”

BEST NOVEL USE OF A DIGITAL METHOD

WINNER

MEASURING MEDIA FREEDOM WITH WORD EMBEDDINGS

Christopher Barrie, Neil Ketchley, Alexandra Siegel and Mossaab Bagdouri

“This is a well-grounded and methodologically innovative study of an important and timely topic.”

“An important and innovative research contribution - impressed by the way in which the project developed something scalable, and cost effective that can be used more widely.”

Highly Commended

The Aesthetics of Agency: Care Identity & Interactive Storytelling

John Morrison

Highly Commended

Incorporating Queer Epistemologies in an Open-Source Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) Language Model: a Pilot Study

Lara Dal Molin

DATA

OUR YEAR IN NUMBERS

We pride ourselves on our momentum and this years numbers continue to reflect growth and lots of engagement. We're working out how best to support our online audiences as we also return to more in-person events, and working out how to balance and make the most of these two spheres. We have more affiliates than ever and maintain our connections with CAHSS Schools and our broader community. Our mailing list has also grown, with over 200 new subscribers this year. As our community becomes more established, we're seeing more return visitors to our website and growing engagement on social media. Our work and community continues to develop as we move forward, and we're excited for what the future holds.

AUDIENCE

- India 3.2%
- Germany 3.5%
- China 5.1%
- US 15.8%
- UK 43.9% (Edinburgh 19%)

Breakdown of the top geographic locations of our web audience

WEBSITE

Recorded visits to the website, showing spikes of 1400+ in September, October, March and April

VISITORS

Total number of visitors

Total number of page views

Unique visitors to website

Returning visitors to website (a huge 17.4%!)

SOCIALS

5,085
PROFILE VIEWS
PER MONTH

+30K
IMPRESSIONS
PER MONTH

2.5%
ENGAGEMENT
RATE

BUDGET MAY 2022 / JULY 2023 BREAKDOWN

TOTAL SPEND £201.5K

- Project Support £1.5K
- Scholarships £8.5K
- Bursaries £5K
- Training £33.5K
- Events £9.5K
- Staff £133K
- Other £3K
- Internships £4K

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🐦 @EDCDCS

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CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY

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